

The Influence of Cultural Values on Intimate Partner Violence Against Women in Nigeria: Evidence from the Literature

Ochuko Oluku¹ and Prof. Edet M. Abasiokong²

^{1&2}Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State, [1ochukooluku2@gmail.com](mailto:ochukooluku2@gmail.com), [2edetabasiokong@gmail.com](mailto:edetabasiokong@gmail.com)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14921875>

Abstract

Intimate partner violence against women (IPV) is a pervasive problem that continues to impose physical, psychological, reproductive, economic and financial consequences on the well-being of women in Nigeria. This paper addresses the role of gender-based cultural values in driving violent behaviours toward female partners in times of conflict. The study is done against the backdrop of efforts to curtail the menace in Nigeria and by extension elsewhere around the world. The paper argues that patriarchal cultural values entrenched in most of Nigeria's indigenous cultures and transmitted inter-generationally help entrench an asymmetrical status/access divide that deepens gender inequalities between men and women and renders women prone to IPV. The study is based on the analysis of secondary data generated from books, newspapers, magazines and the Internet. It recommends better education for women, women empowerment programs, enactment of new/review of old laws that protect women's rights and cultural re-orientation, all aimed at achieving gender parity.

Key Words: *Intimate Partner, Violence, cultural values, Causes, Consequences, Nigeria*

Introduction

Intimate partner violence against women is a global pandemic (Jardin & Jaluegue, 2022) and a pervasive social and public health issue. It is something that affects the family which is the basic unit and cornerstone of society (Weli & Abubaker, 2023). As such, it ultimately threatens the very foundations of society. It is global because its occurrence pervades all races, societies, cultures and communities. It affects women of every race, class, income and other classificatory categories. According to the United Nations (2023), an estimated 736 million women have been subjected to physical or sexual intimate partner violence. In the United States a prevalent rate of violence of male partners against their female spouses stand at between 10% - 15% (Bogat, Antonia & Levendosky, 2015; Bailey & Daugherty, 2007). A World Bank (2022) report states that IPV happens in many ways, from physical, sexual, and emotional to psychological. Instances of abusive acts against women in Nigeria are female genital mutilation, honour killings, forced marriages and sex trafficking. The World Bank estimates the prevalence rate at almost one in three women. 30 per cent of women have experienced intimate partner violence or non-partner violence. Zafar (2020) provides more shocking facts

about violence against women and girls which shows that: 38% of murders of women are committed by male partners; 200 million women and girls have experienced female genital mutilation (FGM); 30% of females globally report that their first experience of sex was forced; women between the ages of 15 and 44 suffer a high risk of rape and domestic violence than other causes; 70 million living women today were married out as children; as much as 150 million girls worldwide are raped or subjected to sexual violence; and up to 10 million children are victims of child sexual exploitation. This is the general picture globally and Nigeria is not left out in this inhuman statistic associated with IPV. Unfortunately, while the data presented above presents alarming public concerns, the problem of abuse and violence against women is showing no sign of abating. Perhaps this is why Akangbe (2020) has noted that IPV is still on the rise globally, spreading like a communicable disease (Naik & Naik, 2016).

In spite of the high and increasing incidence of IPV crimes, most of the cases go unreported. The reason is that there is a culture of silence, tolerance and submissiveness that women are socialized into globally through the institution of patriarchy and male dominance. Among the Vietnamese for instance, studies have shown that their women hold maladaptive beliefs about abuse, e.g. that nothing can be done about it. (Do, Weiss, & Pollack, 2013). In Nigeria, it is generally believed that violence within the family is a private affair. This encourages abusers to continue with abuses while their victims restrain themselves from seeking help for various reasons such as shame of victimization, distrust for law enforcement agencies and societal and religious opinions (Akangbe, 2020).

The influence of cultural beliefs and practices on male violence toward their female partners is therefore widely acknowledged in the literature (Ngoc Do, Weiss and Pollarck, 2013). The reason is not farfetched: man, his personality, behaviour and worldview is a product of his cultural heritage. The reason we are social beings is that we are programmed through socialization to live, think and behave in some culturally predetermined ways. Previous writers on the subject have made attempts to explore this theme in the study of intimate partner violence against women. For instance, Clair (2012) studied how women's cultural background influences their perception of IPV and subsequent adjustment among Latina women. The study found a moderating effect of cultural values on the relationship between exposure to intimate partner aggression and perception of violence. However, this is a perception study of women, based on a culture that is foreign to Nigeria. Other studies have attempted to bridge the geographical and content gap in that work by addressing the cultural issues of IPV in Nigeria. In this regard, Cusairi and Abdullah (2017) researched the influence of cultural practices on

IPV in some communities in Kogi state and revealed the role of cultural practices such as norms of marriage, pre-eminent position of male children and forced marriage in exposing women to violence. Relating Cusairi and Abdullah's work to our current study, one cannot help but identify the limitation in terms of scope and content as the researchers focused on the influencing factors within a narrow study area. In another study, Nwadike and Okoye (2023) examined the role of socio-cultural factors that predispose women to victimization in family matters. Their study is also localized and limited to uncovering the socio-cultural factors behind IPV. One other study by Ajayi, Chantler and Radford (2022) came close to closing this gap because it dwelt on the role of cultural beliefs, norms and practices in Nigerian women's experience of sexual violence. The study was done on Nigerian immigrants in England and was focused only on sexual abuse thus suffering both content and geographical gaps as the first study above. All of the above studies failed to address the primary influence of gender-specific cultural beliefs in the predisposition to violence against women in Nigeria. The current study intends to close this gap by analysing the cultural basis of most IPV cases that occur in Nigeria. The objectives of this paper are to examine the cultural origins of IPV in Nigeria, its prevalence, types, causes and consequences. It is an exploratory research based entirely on information gathered from secondary sources especially the internet, journal articles, newspapers, magazines and books. The data were sorted, arranged thematically and analyzed to provide answers to the above research objectives.

The concept of intimate partner violence (IPV)

There is some confusion about the concept of IPV. This is because several authors use it interchangeably with other concepts, such as 'domestic violence' and 'spousal violence'. IPV embraces both as long as it involves violence among partners in intimate relationships. Intimate partner violence (IPV) refers to abuses or violence that happen within romantic relationships involving one partner against the other, whether their relationship is former or current. Examples of such relationships are marriages, concubinage, dating, and other male-female conjugal friendships. Violence in intimate relationships is known to result in physical, sexual or emotional abuse and controlling behaviour against the victim (WHO, 2012). The problem of IPV is generally regarded as a female issue because women are the worst victims of it. This paper addresses the all-too-common problem of male violence against their female partners in Nigeria.

History and Prevalence of Intimate Partner Violence in Nigeria

Intimate partner violence, like all forms of interpersonal behaviour, is as old as the start of marriages and other forms of intimate relationships that exist between a man and a woman. In the West, the history of IPV is traced to the struggle for social justice and women's rights (Connections for Abused Women and their Children, 2023). There are no documented records of such struggles in Nigeria. Even the advent of legislation against domestic violence can best be described as an emulation of trends in the West.

Intimate partnerships were, and are, outcomes of shared feelings of love between a man and a woman and the need for companionship/childbearing. Customarily, the initial move for intimacy was made by the man directly or through a close friend or relative. The woman is wooed with gifts and pleasant words of love and affection to make her accept the advances of the suitor. In early times, girls rarely accepted such advances without the involvement of their parents. Even if they did, most insisted on the participation of their families before agreeing to sex or cohabitation. That is to say, both families contracted the union of the couple. In traditional societies, men sought partners out of love to raise a family. Therefore, the origin of intimate partner relationships was embedded in culture, and the consummation of the relationship involved several rites and ceremonies. Tradition also placed the men at the head of their families and made women a part of a man's acquisition through marriage. A husband is responsible for the care of his wife, and he exercises total control over her life decisions, such as work, what work to do and who to associate with outside the family circle. Gender norms and roles are so restrictive against women and girls to ensure that they live in compliance with the subservient position allotted to them in the family and the community. Violence against a woman in the home was and is still seen as a private family affair, and wives were groomed to conceal the excesses of their husbands as a sign of honour. Women who transgressed family norms were beaten by their men as a way of discipline. Women are still beaten for such reasons as bad cooking, neglect of children, disobedience, suspicion of infidelity and keeping friends that are unwanted by the husband. Some men even deny their wives sex or lock them up in a room to chastise them. Perpetrators believe they are acting in accordance with tradition (Agbonkhese & Onuoha, 2017, August 24).

These cultural practices apply to other types of intimate relationships that exist in Nigeria, though to a lesser degree. They include concubinage, co-habitation, casual, dating, engagement or courtship and civil unions. Depending on the depth of the relationship, partners may share a lot of things in common in terms of love, family, family ties, businesses, finances, etc. As part

of the dynamics of these relationships, conflicts and disagreements frequently occur over mutual and external issues of the partnership. When not properly managed, they spill over, resulting in violence. Women are at the receiving end in the majority of cases because of their disadvantaged and vulnerable position in the family and the community. The abuses women suffer as a result of violence include molestation, slapping, kicking, rape, murder and acid attacks. Physical harm suffered by victims includes broken skulls and limbs, bruises, cuts, bleeding, burns and death. Others are financial stress and emotional trauma.

The unequal status of women relative to men and the cultural ownership of wives by their husbands virtually places Nigerian men in a domineering position over their female partners. It limits the latter's independence and rights of choice inside the relationship.

There is still a dearth of information on IPV prevalence because of the under-reporting of cases and fear of disclosure due to the cultural acceptance of the phenomenon (Shanko, Wolday, Assefa & Aro, 2013). Data from both the World Bank and WHO show a 30% prevalence rate for women. Studies in Nigeria revealed that about one in four women reported having ever experienced IPV (Benebo, Schumann & Vaezghasemi, 2018). Reports of different studies in the other regions show that the north of the country has a 42% prevalence rate, the south-west 29%, the south-east 78.8%, and the south-south 41% (Oluwole, Onwumelu & Okafor, 2020). The difference in prevalence rates reflects the level of cultural attachments in the regions (Ikekwiibe & Okoror, 2021).

Influence of Culture on IPV Against Women in Nigeria

Intimate partnerships are social or legal unions between two persons. IPV against women is, therefore, a form of behaviour that happens within the context of such romantic relationships. As social and cultural beings, what people are as men or women in relationships and the way they act and respond are defined and moderated by their cultural milieu. Nigeria has over 300 ethnic groups, with a dominance of patriarchal social relations in their family, kinship and community organisation. Statuses, positions, rights, privileges and opportunities ascribed to the two sexes are asymmetrically distributed in favour of men and boys. To men, they are ascribed physical strength, preference, power, dominion and superiority. Women are perceived as 'weaker vessels', inferior, dependents, help-mates and unequal, to be seen and not heard. The structural inequality between the sexes historically curtails women's access to power and opportunity in all institutions and sectors of society. It sets the tone and rationale not only for

the dominance of men over women but also for the abuse of female partners if they disobey or act contrary to the dictates of their men.

Thus cultural/traditional beliefs and practices rationalize IPV against women and makes it a norm. It creates conditions that favour abuses against women (Cusairi & Abdullah, 2017). For instance, a wife must obey her husband or partner in all things, even if she disagrees, and wives are unconditionally obligated to give her husband sex (Ikekwiibe & Okoror, 2021). The payment of bride price on women makes some men see their wives as their property, and unequal partner. Some women, mostly in Igboland, acknowledge that by addressing their husbands as their owners (Alieke, 2022). It is therefore an accepted practice for traditional men to beat their wives as a form of discipline. As it is in the Solomon Islands, various tribes in Nigeria accept wife beating in cases such as unfaithfulness, disobedience and infidelity (Anuk, 2016). Surprisingly, Nigerian women, as in other Sub-Saharan African countries, are more likely to accept IPV than men (Alabi and Ramsden, 2021; Paintsil, Adde, Ameyaw, Dickson and Yaya, 2023). This validates the claim by Cusairi and Abdullah (2017) that domestic violence against women is accepted in Nigeria as normal and part of women. In a study of intimate partner violence among men in a rural community in Oyo State, it was found that a quarter of the men (74%) had perpetrated one form of IPV or the other before the study (Ajibola, Aderonke, Olatayo, Funmito & Gbenga, 2017).

These repressive values that incline men to violence against their partners during conflicts are learnt and imbibed by both genders through socialisation in the family and community. They are also transmitted inter-generationally and so have coalesced as standards for community members to follow. 'Wise' women in the traditional context are those who seek to desist from any liberationist actions that challenge the powers of their partners, even if they are wrong. These anti-women norms and values rationalise the system of patriarchy, male superiority/dominance and female subservience. Originally conceived as the rule of a father in a family or clan, patriarchy is now used to describe the control of the majority of resources in society by men and the subsequent systemic oppression of women (Girum, 2021). This is why most women are poor, relative to their male counterparts, and this (socially engineered) poverty and poor economic conditions are both a risk for and consequence of IPV exposure (Mehr, Bennet, Souza, Buckman, Wild, Marshall, Dams-O'Connor, Esopenko, Price & Tate, 2023).

Evidence of the influence of culture on Nigerian male behaviour toward their female partners is revealed in a study of immigrant Nigerian women in the United States. The study showed that IPV against them is likely when ideologies rooted in the gendered patriarchal culture of

these immigrant families are challenged in the midst of the ideologies of the less patriarchal structure of the U. S. (Kalunta-Crumpton, 2015). Cultural beliefs, standards and practices relegate women to second-class citizens and objectify them for admiration and acquisition where compliant or hate and rejection if not. It could be argued that most violence of men toward their partners, even when offended, is tainted by cultural prejudices about a woman's status, men's sense of entitlement to respect of some sort, and culture-groomed ego. As is with the situation in India (and other developing countries), victims of IPV in Nigeria do not make reports despite the high prevalence (Shah, Catalano, Bhata, Gupta, Daruwalla, Osrin, & Nadkaml, 2024). Many choose to endure the serious abuses they suffer in relationships. According to Collison and Lynam (2021), this is because of a lack of alternatives, e.g. in social and economic support, or because they have too many investments in the relationship, such as children and shared memories. In cases of breakups, the women are left with no means of survival. Except for life-threatening cases, most Nigerian women chose to remain in their marriages.

IPV is, therefore, about power and control (Litner, 2021). It is a pattern of aggressive behaviour in which the more powerful show their authority and power over the weak. A typical example of that, according to Weli and Abubaker (2023), is the honour killing of women in eastern (Muslim) societies. Honour killings permit the brutal murder of a woman for violating cultural norms of acceptable conduct imposed upon women in those societies. An element of that practice also exists in core Muslim areas of northern Nigeria where abdicators/apostates of Islam are lynched or threatened with death. Additionally, the norms of inter-generational marriage that bring together young girls into conjugal unions with more elderly males also increase the risks of abuse (Oyediran, 2021).

Types of Intimate Partner Violence Against Women

Women in Nigeria have always suffered abuses at the hands of male partners from historical times. There are many types of domestic/intimate partner abuse: physical, sexual, emotional/psychological and economic/financial abuse.

Physical abuse: This involves the deliberate use of force or coercion against the intimate partner that causes or is capable of causing injury or harm. The various forms of physical violence, such as slapping, kicking, shoving, punching, locking up and beating, are very common practices against women and children in Nigeria.

Sexual abuse: This is “any sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, or other act directed against a person’s sexuality using coercion, by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim (WHO, 2021). Cases of rape and unwanted fondling of intimate partners are rampant and are often unreported because of shame, unfavourable cultural norms and fear of further victimization.

Psychological/emotional abuse. These are non-physical means that are used by abusers to control, suppress, manipulate, threaten, frighten, monitor, intimidate or humiliate a partner. Women are vulnerable to these and other schemes of male partners in Nigeria because of their relatively low financial capacity, financial /economic dependence and their subservient cultural status in society.

Economic/financial abuse: Our patriarchal society places men in a position to decide whether their spouses should work or shouldn’t, and what work they should or shouldn’t do. This unfair advantage places all men in a position to be potential abusers. Their spouses limit a lot of women with potential, yet use material sustenance as a tool for their continuous manipulation and abuse.

Causes of intimate partner violence against women in Nigeria

Intimate partner violence against women in Nigeria emanates from many sources, such as the exercise of power and control, personality pathology of the perpetrator, cultural/belief influences, and previous exposure to violence (Aidonojie, Majekodunmi, Ikubanni, Oyebade, & Ibrahim, 2022; Idris, Aziz, Khalid, Nizar, Rasip, & Ayub, 2018 and Naik & Naik 2016). The resort to violence in most cases is because women are perceived to be weaker, biologically and culturally and need to be disciplined to keep them within their limits. Owing to this, male abusers are too quick to apply physical force against their female partners or women and girls generally than they do when they are up against their fellow men. Below, we examine various causes of IPV against women in Nigeria.

Personality/Psychological reasons: Perpetrators of domestic violence are believed to suffer psychological problems. Those traits include poor self-esteem, poor impulse control, and sudden bursts of anger or low temperament. These and other personality pathologies are believed to be responsible for the male victimisation of their female partners.

Jealousy: Domestic intimate partner violence is often caused by a jealous partner who suspects the other of infidelity or of wanting to quit the relationship. The results are tantrums of anger,

usually resulting in violence and aggression against the victim. Studies confirm a high prevalence of romantic jealousy in Nigeria with a strong link of romantic jealousy to personality traits and cultural orientation (Ayoade, Akpune, Akinnawo, & Akintola, 2023).

Social stress: Many domestic violence in Nigeria are thought to be a response to the stress couples go through in the family. When some men are no longer able to cope with the pressure of the burden of relationships, finances, or other matters, violence becomes a means of dissipating the pressure.

Social learning from parents: Many abusers are believed to have observed and learnt the behaviour as children from their parents or guardians while growing up. Researches in Nigeria confirm this. Studies found that exposure to violence as a child increases the chances of IPV (Okedare & Fawole, 2023;)

Power and control: Abusive behaviours are considered a means by abusers to secure control over their partners. Bolstered by the prevailing culture of patriarchy, insecure males often use violence as an instrument to bring their partners under their control.

Alcohol/Drug abuse: The abuse of drugs and alcohol has been found in many studies to be associated with the perpetration of partner abuse (for instance, Okedare & Fawole, 2023). Substance abuse is prominent in male IPV, while it plays a substantial role in keeping women in IPV relationships (Bennett & Bland, 2008). The potency of addiction to substances in fuelling male IPV is demonstrated in a case in Nigeria cited by Aidonojie, Majekodunmi, Ikubanni, Oyebade, & Ibrahim (2022), where a battered woman was granted her plea for divorce by a court over her husband's addiction to drugs.

Beliefs: Many cultural beliefs discriminate against women and restrict their liberties. Any breaches of those prejudicial norms are usually met with brutal consequences. The belief in Nigeria, for instance, that a woman is part of a man's possessions enables men to use coercion to mould women in line with how they want them to live as their wives. Wife abuse commonly manifests in the form of battery, torture, acid bath, beating, choking, rape and sometimes death (Aidonojie, Majekodunmi, Ikubanni, Oyebade, & Ibrahim 2022).

Childlessness and male child syndrome: In Nigeria, children are a sustaining and stabilising factor in marriage. Even when the marriage is blessed with children, the absence of a male child is problematic for most men and could be a source of abuse for the woman from her husband and his relatives.

Victim characteristics: Studies have also revealed the characteristics of women who are more likely to be prone to domestic violence. They include women with primary education, women living in cities or in the south-south, Christian women, women whose husbands consume alcohol and women who witnessed domestic violence in their childhood (Oyediran, 2021).

Consequences of IPV against women in Nigeria

The definition of the WHO (2022) of intimate violence against women specifies several negative and harmful consequences: the “behaviour within intimate relationships that causes physical, sexual or psychological harm”. The US Department of Justice (2020), on its part, notes that violence perpetuated against women is often followed by emotionally abusive and controlling behaviour. The wide and varied range of consequences has made violence against women attract the research attention of diverse academic fields such as sociology, medicine, psychiatry, criminology and law. These consequences are without prejudice to nationality, race, religion, etc. Their applicability to Nigeria is confirmed by numerous indigenous studies, such as the ones by Issah, Yeboa, Kpordoxah, Boah and Mahama (2022) and Okedare and Fawole (2023). Drawing from the literature, some of the consequences highlighted are:

Physical, health and reproductive consequences: Several studies in Nigeria provide supportive evidence on the physical, health and reproductive consequences of IPV (Antai, 2011; Onoh, Umeora, Ezeonu, Onyebuchi, Lawani, & Agwu, 2013). IPV has significant health effects on women in Nigeria. Violence results in physical injuries, many of which are life-threatening, often leading to death. Such injuries include cuts, bruises, broken bones, headaches, and brain injuries. There are also risks to mental health that result, with many women suffering from mood disorders, anxiety, PTSD and depression. There are also severe consequences on sexual and reproductive health. They include trauma in the regions of the vagina, urethra and anus. Women also experience issues of unwanted pregnancies and venereal diseases, including HIV/AIDs.

Social and behavioural consequences: The World Health Organization’s (2022) report on IPV indicates that it carries a lot of social and behavioural problems, namely, subsequent violence, victimization, internalising behaviour problems and unplanned pregnancies. Female victims are at risk of suffering from substance misuse as well as of transitioning from substance misuse to substance abuse disorder with lasting mental and physical health consequences (Mehr, Bennet, de Souza, Buckman, Wilde, Marshall, Dams-O’Connor, Esopenko, Price, &

Tate, 2003). Many women victims involved in substance use do so as a way of coping, while abusive partners coerce others.

Impact on children: Research has shown that violence against women has a negative effect on the health and well-being of the children who witness it. Witnessing IPV is associated with mental distress in adolescents and young adults. This was revealed in a cross-sectional study carried out in Cambodia, Malawi and Nigeria (Kieselbach, Kress, MacMillan & Perneger, (2021). Another study conducted in Ibadan, Nigeria, found that IPV against women affects the nutritional status of the affected women and their children, making the children less likely to be underweight (Issah, Yeboa, Kpordoxah, Boah, & Mahama, 2022). These are some of the effects of domestic violence resulting in physical and mental abuse, crises in the family, separation and divorce. Some children imbibe violence, become wayward, and eventually turn to criminal adaptations out of loss of home discipline and parental neglect from the breakdown of the family.

Impact on the family and society: Violence degrades the bonds of relationships that exist between couples and their households. Since the family is the basic unit of society, the high prevalence of intimate partner violence is silently causing widespread social disorganisation through intra-family disaffection, loss of commitment to family values, interpersonal and inter-family conflicts, increasing cases of marital infidelity, separation of couples, high divorce rates, broken homes, neglect of children and child delinquency.

Economic and financial consequences: The patriarchal system in Nigeria and the culture of wife subservience/dependence on husbands restricts and limits women's engagement in productive activities that can enhance their financial solvency and self-reliance. This makes them vulnerable to abuse. In the event of divorce or separation, most are left with nothing and so suffer a lack of care and resources to cater for themselves and their children. Some abusive men also use financial deprivation as a weapon to keep their wives under their subjection. Poverty and poor economic conditions are both a risk for and consequence of IPV exposure (Mehr, Bennet, de Souza, Buckman, Wilde, Marshall, Dams-O'Connor, & Tate, 2023).

Implications for the Containment of the Problem.

Inculcated and imbibed traditional values about the status and role of women relative to men, as well as cultural acceptance of IPV against women, as we have seen in our analysis, has serious consequences for efforts to contain the problem. First, tradition and cultural norms still validate the perpetration of abuses and continue to embolden traditionally minded perpetrators

in Nigeria. Second, it intimidates women into submitting to the whims and caprices of their partners in order to escape their abuses. Abuse victims are even scared to report their ordeals because that in itself is interpreted as an act of disrespect for the partner, his family and the community. The hopeful side is that IPV is lower where there is less attachment to culture and tradition, as revealed in the differential prevalence rates for the regions of the country. In other words, the more society embraces modernity over tradition, the lower the incidence of IPV against women. Equally, studies reveal that women with enhanced social demographics, such as higher education and good access to economic opportunities, are less prone to poverty and abuse (Onoh, Umeora, Ezeonu, Onyebuchi, Lawani & Agwu, 2013; Mbadugha, 2016; Oyediran, Odutolu & Atobatele, 2011).

Conclusion

Intimate partner violence against women is a pervasive problem with physical, psychological, reproductive, economic and financial consequences on the well-being of women in Nigeria. Victims suffer all kinds of abuses, from beatings, threats, molestations, rape, financial deprivations and death in the extremity of cases. This study explored the role of tradition and cultural values in the perpetration of IPV by men against their partners. IPV against women, we have argued, is an expression of a culturally sanctioned quest by men to maintain their dominance over their partners in our largely patriarchal societies. Male cultural arrogance and sense of entitlement against women added to other factors such as personality pathologies of male abusers, jealousy, social/ financial stress, exposure of abuser to violence early in life, and alcohol/substance abuse are also contributory factors. The consequences of abuse spread beyond the victims to their children and society at large. Yet most victims refuse to report and stand against the abuses for reasons bordering on cultural restraints, fear of reprisals, lack of alternatives and the investments they made in the relationship.

Recommendations

As a contribution toward the mitigation of the problem, this paper recommends the following:

- i.** The promotion of better education for women and girls.
- ii.** Provide more economic and political opportunities to women to balance the balance of power between the sexes and enhance gender parity.
- iii.** The enactment of new and strengthening of old laws that prohibit abuse of women and men.

- iv. Promotion of women's rights through cultural reorientation and educational and other empowerment programs that can engender gender equality.

References

- Agbonkhese, J. & Onuoha, C. (2017). Does Nigerian culture permit domestic violence? *Vanguard News* Retrieved from: <https://www.vanguardngr.com>>woman
- Alabi T. A. & Ramsden, M. J. (2021). Gender differences in the acceptance of wife-beating in Nigeria: Evidence from the 2018 Demographic and Health Survey, *Heliyon*, 7(10) doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08191.
- Alieke, S. (2022, April 13). *Law, culture and tradition as the enablers of domestic violence in Nigeria*, Retrieved from: <https://www.tekedia.com>>communityinsights
- Antai, D. (2011). Traumatic physical health consequences of intimate partner violence against women: what is the role of community-level factors? *BMC Women's Health*, doi: 10.1186/1472-6874-1156. PMID: 22185323; PMCID: PMC3260128.
- Ayoade, O. O., Akpune, B. C., Akinnawo, E., & Akintola, A. (2023). Correlates of Romantic Jealousy Among Nigerian Adults in Romantic Relationships, *Redeemer's University Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 6(2), <https://runjmss.com>>index.php>runojs>article>view
- Aidonojie, P. A., Majekodunmi, T. A., Ikubanni, O. O., Oyebade, A. A. & Ibrahim, N. (2022). The causes of the rising incidence of domestic violence in Nigeria: Proposing judicial separation as a panacea, *Journal HukumUnissula*, 38(2), 99 DOI:10.26532/lh.v38i2.21592
- Akangbe, T. A. (2020). Culture, religion and help-seeking for intimate partner violence victims in Nigeria, *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 3(2), 56-62.
- Bailey, B. A., & Daugherty, R. A. (2007). Intimate partner violence during pregnancy: Incidence and associated health behaviours in a rural population. *Maternal Child Health Journal*, 11(5), 495-503.
- Benebo, F. O., Schumann, B. & Vaezghasemi, M. (2018). Intimate partner violence against women in Nigeria: a multilevel study investigating the effect of women's status and community norms, *BMC Women's Health*, 18(134). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-018-0628-7>.
- Bennet, L. & Bland, P. (2008). Substance abuse and intimate partner violence, Retrieved 16/2/2024 from: <https://vawnet.org>>material>subst...
- Bogat, G. A., Antonia, M. G., & Levendosky, A. A. (2015). Assessment and psychotherapy with women experiencing intimate partner violence: Integrating research and practice. *The American Academy of Psychoanalysis and Dynamic Psychiatry* 4(2), 189-218.
- Collison, K. L. & Lynam, D. R. (2021). Personality Disorders as Predictors of Intimate Partner Violence: A Meta-analysis, *Clinical Psychology Review*, 88 doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2021.102047.
- Connections for Abused Women and their Children (2023). Things to Know about the History of the Domestic Violence Movement, retrieved from: <https://www.cawc.org>>news>things -to-know-about-t...
- Dizon, L. & Graham-Kevan (2011). Understanding the nature and etiology of intimate partner violence and implications for practice and policy, *Clinical Psychology Review*, 31(7), 1145-1155
- Do, K. N., Weiss, B. & Pollack, A., (2013). Cultural beliefs, intimate partner violence, and mental health functioning among Vietnamese women, Retrieved 7/2/2024 from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc>

- Dodd, L. W. (2009). Therapeutic group work with young children and mothers who have experienced domestic abuse. *Education Psychology in Practice*, 25 (21):21-36
- Dutton, D. G. (1995). Male abusiveness in intimate relationships, *Clinical Psychology Review*, 15(6), 567-581.
- Enimapopo, E. T. & Nwamadi, L. (2023). Causes and consequences of domestic violence among married women in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*, <https://saudijournals.com> Doi 10.36348/jaep.2023.vo7i05.006
Retrieved from: <https://westernu.ca>2023/12>.
- Esere, M. O., Idowu, A. I., Durosaro, I. A. & Omotosho, J. A. (2017). Causes and consequences of intimate partner rape and violence: Experience of victims in Lagos, Nigeria, *African Journal of Aids and HIV Research*, 5(2), 233-239
- Gant, A. M. S. (1991). *Domestic violence against women as human rights violation, decision of the superior tribunal of justice, Brazil's highest Court of Appeal, Brazilia*. Retrieved 20/2/2024 from: <https://www.coreidh.or.cr>...>
- Gary, A., Kipper, V., Geist, R., & Rice, L., (2023). *Intimate partner violence: Warning signs and interventions*. Wolters Kluwer Health, Inc.
- Girum, H. (2021). How Patriarchal System Affect Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) in Sub-Saharan Africa, Retrieved from: <https://tayaeth.org>>news>how-p...>
- Gupta, S. (2023). *Understanding intimate partner violence*. Retrieved 7/2/2024 from: www.bmcwomenhealthbiomedcentral.com.
- Idris, S. A. M., Aziz, N. N. A., Khalid, R. K., Nizar, N. F. M., Rasip, K. A., & Ayub, W. (2018). Causes and effects of domestic violence: A conceptual model on the performance at Work. *International Journal for Studies on Children, Women, Elderly and Disabled*, 4 Retrieved 10/10/2024 from: <https://www.researchgate.net>323...>
- Ikekwi, I. C. & Okoror, C. E. M. (2021). The pattern and socio-cultural determinants of intimate partner violence in a Nigerian rural community. *African Journal of Primary Health & Family Medicine*, 13(1) Retrieved 16/10/2024 from: <http://www.scielo.org.za>scielo>.
- Issah, A. N., Yeboa, D., Kpordoxah, M. R., Boah, M. & Mahama, A. B. (2022). *Association between exposure to intimate partner violence and the nutritional status of women and children in Nigeria*, Retrieved from <https://journals.plos.org>article>jo...>
- Jardin, R. A., & Jaluague, J. A. (2022). Inner strength and coping strategies of women victims of domestic violence in Cebu City, Philippines. *Human Behaviour, Development and Society*, 23(3), 44-65.
- Kallunta-Crumpton, A. (2015), Intersections of Patriarchy, National Origin, and Immigrant Nigerian Women's Experience of Intimate Partner Violence in the United States, *International Journal of the Sociology of the Family*, 41(1): 1-29, Retrieved 25/10/2024 from: <https://www.serialsjournals.com>...>
- Kieselbach, B., Kress, H., MacMillan, H., & Perneger, T. (2021). Prevalence of childhood exposure to intimate partner violence and association with mental distress in Cambodia, Malawi and Nigeria: A cross-sectional study, *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 111 Retrieved 25/12/2024 from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>...>
- Litner, J. (2021). What causes domestic violence? Retrieved 14/2/2024 from: <https://psychocentral.com>lib>wha...>
- Mbadugha, E. I. (2016). Intimate partner violence and sexual violence against women: Any end in sight? *International Journal of Medicine and Bio-medical Research*, 5(1) Retrieved 22/10/2024 from: <https://www.ajol.info>view>
- Maguele, M. S. (2023). *Evidence of sociocultural factors influencing intimate partner violence among young women in sub-Saharan Africa: A scoping review*. BMJ Publishing Group Ltd.

- Mehr, J. B., Bennet, E. R., de Souza, N. L., Buckman, J. F., Wilde, E. A., Marshall, A. D., Dams-O'Connor, K., J. L., Esopenko, C., Price, & Tate, D. F. (2023). *Intimate partner violence, substance use and health comorbidities among women: A narrative review*. Retrieved 16/2/2024 from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>pmc>.
- Mohamedamin, P. F. & Fatahi, N. (2022). Relationship between personality traits and violence involvement: A study of high school students in northern Iraq. *Journal of Academy of Medical Sciences of Bosnia Herzegovina*, 30(3), 213-219.
- MSFD (2024). Spousal abuse, Retrieved from: <https://www.msfd.gov.sg>what-we-do>domestic-violence>.
- Naik, I. B. & Naik, A. R. (2016). Domestic violence its causes, consequences and preclusions strategies, *IJARIE*, 2(2) Retrieved 12/10/2024 from: <https://ijarile.com>FormDetails>
- Okedare, O. O. & Fawole, O. I (2023). Intimate partner violence among young women in Ibadan, Nigeria: are there slum or non-slum differences? *BMC Womens Health*, Retrieved from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>pmc>
- Oluwole, E. O., Onwumelu, N. G. & Okafor, I. P. (2020). Prevalence and determinants of IPV among adult women in an urban community in Lagos, South-West Nigeria, *Pan African Medical Journal*, Vol. 36 No 345
- Onoh, R. C., Umeora, O., Ezeonu, P., Onyebuchi, A., Lawani, O. & Agwu, U. (2013). Prevalence, pattern and consequences of intimate partner violence during pregnancy at Abakaliki Southeast Nigeria, *Annals of Medical & Health Sciences Research*, 3(4): 484-491.
- Oyediran, K. (2021). Intimate partner violence in Nigeria. In *International Perspectives on Intimate Partner Violence, Challenges and Opportunities*, Stith M. & Spencer, C. M. (Ed.). Retrieved 9/1/2024 from: <https://www.researchgate.net>3548...>
- Oyediran, K. A., Odutolu, O., Atobatele, (2011). Inter-generational sexual relationship in Nigeria: implications for negotiating safe sexual practices, social and psychological aspects of HIV/AIDS and their ramifications, In G. Letamo (Ed.), *Social and Psychological aspects of HIV/AIDS and their ramifications*. Tech Open Access Publisher.
- Paintsil, J. A. Adde, K. S., Ameyaw, E. K., Dickson, K. S. & Yaya, S. (2023). Gender differences in the acceptance of wife-beating: evidence from 30 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, *BMC Women's Health*, 23(415) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-023-02611-w>
- Shah, A. H., Catalano, A., Bhata, U., Gupta, D., Daruwalla, N., Osrin, D., & Nadkaml, A., (2024). Coping strategies and help-seeking behaviours among survivors of intimate partner violence: A qualitative study of spouses of men with heavy drinking in India, *Health & Social Care in the Community*, Retrieved from <https://www.hindawi.comjournals/hsc2024/683978/>
- Shanko, W. Wolday, M., Assefa, N. & Aro, A. R. (2013). Domestic Violence Against Women in Kersa, Oromia Region, Eastern Ethiopia, *PubMed*, 19(1), -23
- Tanimu, T. S., Yohanna, S. & Omeiza, S. Y. (2016). The pattern and correlates of intimate partner violence among women in Kano, Nigeria, *African Journal of Primary Health Care Fam Med*, 8 (1) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>...>
- U N Women (2023). *Facts and figures: Ending violence against women*. Retrieved 7/2/2024 from: <https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/ending-violence-against-women/facts-and-figures>
- Weli, E. M. & Abubaker, S. S. (2023). The Legal Confrontation of Domestic Violence: A Comparative Study Between Iraq and Italy, *LactioSocialis*, 7(1), 21-30
- WHO (2021). *Violence against women*, Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int>...> Detail
- WHO (2012). *Understanding and addressing violence against women*, Retrieved from: <https://apps.who.int>violence-info>intimate-partner-violence...>

World Health Organization. (2010). *Preventing intimate partner and sexual violence against women: taking action and generating evidence*. Geneva.
http://www.who.int/violence_injury_prevention/publications/violence/97892415607_eng.pdf